

ARTICLE

Rainfall Probability Analysis for Crop Planning in Ganjam District of Hirakud Command Area of Odisha, India

C.R.Subudhi^{1,‡,*}, Sukanya Suryavanshi^{1,‡} & Nibedita Jena^{1,‡}

¹Department of SWCE, CAET, OUAT, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

*rsubudhi5906@gmail.com. ‡Contributed equally.

Received: December 30, 2019; Accepted: February 06, 2020; Published: February 14, 2020;

Abstract

This study was undertaken in the U.G. thesis work in the Dept. Of SWCE, CAET, OUAT, Bhubaneswar during the year 2018-19. Ganjam district has latitude of 19°23'15"N and a longitude of 85°03'05"E. The average rainfall in Anugul district is around 1132.7 mm, though it receives high amount rainfall, but most of the rainfall occurred during Kharif. So most of the crops get a low yield due to improper crop planning. Thus, this study is proposed to be undertaken with the following objective: Probability analysis of annual, seasonal and monthly rainfall data of Ganjam district. So rainfall data were collected from OUAT, Agril Meteorology Dept. from 2001 to 2017 (17 years) monthly, seasonal and annual rainfall was analysed. Probability analysis has been made and equations were fitted to different distributions and best fitted equations were tested. Monthly, Annual and seasonal probability analysis of rainfall data shows the probability rainfall distribution of Ganjam district in different months, years and seasons. It is observed that rainfall during June to Sep is slightly less than 1000 mm and cropping pattern like paddy (110 days) may be followed by mustard is suitable for this region. Also, if the kharif rain can be harvested and it can be reused for another rabbi crop by using a sprinkler or drip irrigation, which will give benefit to the farmers. Annual rainfall of Ganjam district is 1132.7 mm at 50% probability level.

Key words: Rainfall; Probability Analysis; Crop Planning, Command Area, Hidaka

Introduction

Ganjam district has latitude of 20°50'40"N and a longitude of 85°09'04"E. The average rainfall in Ganjam district is around 1132.7 mm, most of the rainfall occurred during kharif. Thus, this study is proposed to be undertaken with the following objective: Probability analysis of annual, seasonal and monthly rainfall data of Ganjam district.

Thom (1966) employed mixed gamma probability distribution for describing skewed rainfall data and employed approximate solution to non-linear equations obtained by differentiating log likelihood function with respect to the parameters of the distribution. Subsequently, this system along the side variance ratio test as a goodness-of-fit has been widely employed (Car et al. (2004), Jat et al. (2006), Senapati et al. (2009) applied incomplete gamma probability distribution for rainfall analysis. Additionally to gamma probability distribution, another two-parametric probability distributions (normal, log-normal, Weibull, smallest and largest extreme value), and three-parameter probability distributions (lognormal, gamma, log-logistic and Weibull) are widely used for studying flood frequency, drought

analysis and rainfall probability analysis (Senapati et al. 2009) Gumbel (1954) Chow (1964), have applied gamma distribution with two and three parameter, Pearson type-III, extreme value, binomial and Poisson distribution of hydrological data.

Materials and Methods

The data were collected from the District Collector's Office, Ganjam district for this study. Rainfall data for 17 years from 2001 to 2017 are collected for the presented study to make rainfall forecasting through different methods

Probability Distribution Functions

For seasonal rainfall analysis of Anugul block, three seasons- kharif (June -September), Rabi (October to January) and summer (February to May) are considered. The data is fed into the Excel spreadsheet, where it's arranged during a chronological order and therefore the Weibull plotting position formula is then applied. The Weibull plotting position formula is given by

$$p = \frac{m}{N+1} \quad (1)$$

Where m=rank number N=number of years The recurrence interval is given by

$$T = \frac{1}{p} = \frac{N+1}{m} \tag{2}$$

The values are then subjected to various probability distribution functions, namely- normal, log-normal (2- parameter), log-normal (3-parameter), gamma, generalized extreme value, Weibull, generalized Pareto distribution, Pearson, log-Pearson type-III and Gumbel distribution. Some of the probability distribution functions are described as follows:

Normal Distribution

The probability density is

$$p(x) = (1/\sigma\sqrt{2\pi})e^{-(x-\mu)^2/2\sigma^2} \tag{3}$$

Where x is the variant, is the mean value of variety and is the standard deviation. In this distribution, the mean, mode and median are the same. The cumulative probability of a value being equal to or less than x is

$$p(x \leq) = 1/\sigma\sqrt{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^x e^{-(x-\mu)^2/2\sigma^2} dx \tag{4}$$

This represents the area under the curve between the variates of $-\infty$ and x.

Log-normal (2-parameter) Distribution

The probability density is

$$p(x) = (1/\sigma_y e^y \sqrt{2\pi}) e^{-(y-\mu_y)^2/2\sigma_y^2} \tag{5}$$

Where $y = \ln x$, where x is the variate, μ_y is the mean of y and σ_y is the standard deviation of y.

Log-normal (3-parameter) Distribution

A random variable X is said to have three-parameter log-normal probability distribution if its probability density function (pdf) is given by:

$$f(x) = \left\{ \frac{1}{(x-\lambda)\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\log(x-\lambda) - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^2 \right\}, \lambda < x < \infty, \right. \\ \left. \mu > 0, \sigma > 0 \right\} \tag{6}$$

Where μ , σ and λ are known as location, scale and threshold parameters, respectively.

Pearson Distribution

The general and basic equation to define the probability density of a Pearson distribution

$$p(x) = e \int_{-\infty}^x \frac{a+x}{b_0 + b_1x + b_2x^2} dx \tag{7}$$

Where a, b_0, b_1 and b_2 are constants The criteria for determining types of distribution are β_1, β_2 and k where

$$\beta_1 = \frac{\mu_3^2}{\mu_2^3} \tag{8}$$

$$\beta_2 = \frac{\mu_4}{\mu_2^2} \tag{9}$$

$$k = \frac{\beta_1(\beta_2 + 3)^2}{4(4\beta_2 - 3\beta_1)(2\beta_2 - 3\beta_1 - 6)} \tag{10}$$

Where μ_2, μ_3 and μ_4 are second, third and fourth moments about the mean.

Log-Pearson Type III Distribution

In this the variable is first transformed into logarithmic form (base 10) and the transformed data is then analyzed. If X is the variant of a random hydrologic series, then the series of Z variates where $z = \log x$ Are first obtained. For this z series, for any recurrence interval T and the coefficient of skew C_s ,

$$\sigma = \text{Standard deviation of the Z variate sample} \\ = \sqrt{\sum (z - \bar{z})^2 / (N - 1)} \text{ and } C_s = \text{coefficient of skew of variate Z} \\ = \frac{N \sum (z - \bar{z})^3}{(N-1)(N-2)\sigma_z^3} \\ \bar{Z} = \text{mean of z values} \\ N = \text{sample size} = \text{number of years of record}$$

Generalized Pareto Distribution

The family of generalized Pareto distributions (GPD) has three parameters μ, σ, ξ .

The cumulative distribution function is

$$F_{(\xi, \mu, \sigma)}(x) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1 - \left(1 + \frac{\xi(x-\mu)}{\sigma}\right)^{-\frac{1}{\xi}} \text{ for } \xi \neq 0 \\ 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right) \text{ for } \xi = 0 \end{array} \right\} \tag{11}$$

For $x \geq \mu$ when $\xi \geq 0$ and $x \leq \mu - \frac{\sigma}{\xi}$ when $\xi < 0$, where $\mu \in \mathbf{R}$ is the location parameter, $\sigma > 0$ the scale parameter and $\xi \in \mathbf{R}$ the shape parameter. The probability density function is

$$f_{(\xi, \mu, \sigma)}(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(1 + \frac{\xi(x-\mu)}{\sigma}\right)^{-\left(\frac{1}{\xi} + 1\right)} \tag{12}$$

Or

$$f_{(\xi, \mu, \sigma)}(x) = \frac{\sigma^{-\frac{1}{\xi}}}{(\sigma + \xi(x-\mu))^{\left(\frac{1}{\xi} + 1\right)}} \tag{13}$$

Again, for $x \geq \mu$, and $x \leq \mu - \frac{\sigma}{\xi}$ when $\xi < 0$

Result and Discussion

The various parameters like mean, standard deviation, RMSE value, were obtained and noted for different distributions. For generalized extreme value and generalized Pareto distribution the other parameters like shape parameter, scale parameter and location parameter are also noted for further calculation. A similar procedure is followed for the seasonal, annual and pointed analysis. The rainfall at 90%, 75 %, 50%, 25% and 10% probability levels are determined. The distribution "best" fitted to the data is noted down in a tabulated form in Table 1. In the present study, the parameters of the distri-

Figure 1. Rainfall at 50% Probabilities (Monthly) at Ganjam district

Table 1. Rainfall Analysis of Ganjam District at Different Probability Levels for Different Months and Season

Months	Best fit Distribution	RMSE Value	Rainfall at probability levels				
			90%	75%	50%	25%	10%
January	Pareto	0.07416	-	-	-	11.36	33.41
February	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
March	Pareto	0.06573	-	-	-	10.27	28.07
April	EV type III	0.04972	-	-	-	48.21	74.41
May	Pareto	0.0335	-	-	36.15	100.23	155.94
June	Log normal	0.0582	50.33	73.00	110.35	166.84	242.10
July	Pareto	0.0355	75.09	106.03	171.64	274.28	393.40
August	Pareto	0.05654	79.38	134.84	227.72	321.46	378.47
September	Ln(3-P)	0.06156	73.52	117.40	176.92	250.32	330.98
October	EV type III	0.036	16.53	59.80	146.17	281.21	447.95
November	Gamma	0.06123	-	-	23.40	94.78	198.58
December	Gamma	0.08322	-	-	-	3.28	36.55
Annual	Pareto	0.04857	651.94	833.19	1132.7	1427.47	1600.23
Kharif	Log normal	0.4594	480.77	583.94	724.8	899.59	1092.93
Rabi	Pareto	0.03947	47.33	108.32	232	409.73	592.04
Summer	Pareto	0.03009	2.17	31.85	84	142.49	183.38

bution for the various distributions are estimated by FLOOD-flood frequency analysis software. The rainfall data is that the input to the software programme. The simplest fitted distribution of various month and season and annual were presented in Table 1.

The annual rainfall in 50% probability was found to be 1132.7 mm for Ganjam district of Odisha. During Kharif at 50% probability level, the rainfall is 724.8 mm, whereas only 232mm and 84 mm was received during Rabi and summer respectively, so water harvesting structures may be made to grow crops during Rabi and summer to utilise the water from the water harvesting structures to increase the cropping intensity of the area. It is also observed that at the 75 % probability level the July, Aug and Sept received more than 100 mm, so farmers of these areas can grow crops in upland areas suitably paddy can be grown followed by any rabbi crop in Rabi season like mustard or quality in upland areas. In Figure 1 the plot between different months and amount of rainfall in different probabilities were shown, it is observed that August month gets highest amount of rainfall compared to other months.

Conclusion

Forecasting of rainfall is essential for proper planning of crop production. About 70% of the cultivable land of Odisha depending on rainfall for crop production. Prediction of rainfall in advance helps to accomplish the agricultural operations in time. It can be concluded that, excess runoff should be harvested for irrigating post-monsoon crops. It becomes highly necessary to provide the farmers with high-yielding variety of crops and such varieties which require less water and are early-maturing in Ganjam district of the Hirakud command area of Odisha. It is also observed that at the 75% probability level the June, July, Aug and Sept received more than 100 mm, so farmers of these areas can grow crops in upland areas, suitably paddy can be grown followed by any rabbi crop in Rabi season like mustard or quality in upland areas. Annual rainfall of Ganjam district is 1132.7 mm at 50% probability level. It is observed that August month gets highest amount of rainfall compared to other months.

References

1. Biswas, B. (1990). Forecasting for agricultural application. *Mausam* 41(2), 329–334.
2. Chow, V. (1964). *Hand book of Applied Hydrology*. McGraw Hill Book Co.
3. Das, M. (1992). *Analysis of agrometeorological data of Bhubaneswar for crop planning*. C.A.E.T., OUAT.
4. Gumbel, E. (1954). *Statistical theory of droughts*. *Proceedings of ASCE* 439, 1–19.
5. Gumbel, E. (1958). *Statistics of extreme*. Columbia University

Press, New York.

6. Harshfield, D. and Kohlar, M. (1960). An empirical appraisal of the Gumbel extreme procedure. *J. of Geophysics Research* 65, 1737–1746.
7. Jat, M. L., Singh, R. V., Balyan, J. K., Jain, L. and Sharma, R. (2006). Analysis of weekly rainfall for Sorghum based crop planning in Udaipur region. *Indian J. Dryland Agric. Res. Dev* 21, 114–122.
8. Kar, G., Singh, R. and Verma, H. (2004). Alternative cropping strategies for assured and efficient crop production in upland rain fed rice areas of eastern India based on rainfall analysis. *J. of Geophysics Research* 67, 47–62.
9. Panigrahi, B. (1998). Probability analysis of short duration rainfall for crop planning in coastal Orissa. *Indian J. Soil Cons.*, 26, 178–182.
10. Reddy, S. (1999). *Principles of Agronomy*. 1st edition. Kalyani publication.
11. Sadhab, P. (2002). *Study of rainfall distributions and determination of drainage coefficient: A case study for coastal belt of Orissa*. C.A.E.T., OUAT.
12. Senapati, S. C. and Sahu, A.Pand Sharma, S. (2009). Analysis of meteorological events for crop planning in rain fed uplands. *Indian J. Soil Cons.*, 37, 178–182.
13. Sharda, V. and Das, P. (2005). Modeling weekly rainfall data for crop planning in a sub-humid climate of India. *Agricultural Water Management* 76, 120–138.
14. Subramanya, K. (1990). *Engineering Hydrology*. 23rd reprint. Tata Mc-graw Hill Publishing Company Ltd.
15. Subudhi, C. (2007). Probability analysis for prediction of annual maximum daily rainfall of Chakapada block of Kandhamal district of Orissa. *Indian J. Soil Cons.*, 35, 84–85.
16. Subudhi, C., Suryavansi, S. and Jena, N. (2019). Rainfall probability analysis for crop planning in Anugul block of Anugul district of Hirakud command area of Odisha, India. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 8, 49–54.
17. Thom, H. (1966). *Some methods of climatological analysis*. WMO Tech.
18. Weibull, W. (1951). A statistical distribution functions of wide applicability. *J. Appl. Mech* 18, 293–297.